

Developing Teaching Media Using *Anime* as English Grammar Teaching Material

Nur Annisa¹, Indawan Syahri², Rini Susanti³

^{1,2,3}(English education study program, Universitas Muhammadiyah Palembang, Indonesia)

ABSTRACT: This study aims at (1) developing teaching media using Anime for grammar lesson; and (2) investigating the feasibility of learning media in the delivery of the grammar materials. This study used a development model that refers to the development of 4D (four-D) model Thiagarajan (1974), which includes four stages. They are: (1) define; (2) design; (3) develop; and (4) disseminate. To investigate the feasibility of the design, questionnaires were given to the expert validators (material and media) and students. The results showed that both material and media experts validated the Anime designed in this study to be "very feasible." Students' feedback also indicated no problem found with "very feasible" level, which means that Anime designed in this study is good to be used as the teaching media in grammar class.

KEYWORDS—Teaching media; Anime; Grammar

I. INTRODUCTION

Grammar is one of the essential skill that students should master. The skills deal with how to form sentences and use them appropriately. Grammar is a collection of rules for combining words in a language into larger entities. Grammar plays a significant role in genre-based teaching and learning. Now, the text-based approach is applied in Indonesia Education System. Since junior high school, students are introduced to text such as descriptions, recounts, reports, and narratives. As language competence, grammar is included in the texts. Without having a good understanding of grammar, students will be challenging to understand some text or dialogue. Therefore, grammar mastery is very necessary to achieve language competency.

Most Indonesian students face difficulties in learning structure because the grammatical rules of Bahasa Indonesia are different from those of English. It is one of the problems encountered by students of senior high school. It is the evidence why they become passive, confused, shy, afraid of making mistakes, and feel bored when they study English grammar, and sometimes they are sleepy in the class when they are studying. It can lead the learners to get negative results; they become unmotivated to learn and cannot communicate in English. Those grammar problems must be solved because it can be difficult for the students to continue the next level or grade. One of the teaching strategies that can motivate students to learn English is using the media such as video.

Nowadays, people can make video easily. They can combine their video with pictures, music, and sound. One day, the writers told her hobby of watching Anime to her lecturer. Her lecturer suggested making Anime as the writers's topic in the thesis. Then the writers tried to combine video with *Anime*. *Anime* ("ah-nemay") refers to Japanese animated film and television, but the worlds of *Anime* extend well beyond what appears on the screen. In its interwoven commercial and cultural activity webs that span industries and national lines, *Anime* is typical of contemporary media (Coudry, 2013). *Anime* is a video animation made in Japan. *Anime* exists around the world, including Indonesia. In Indonesia, *Anime* has existed since 1980. *Anime* will be more interesting if it is designed into a teaching media as an efficient and creative learning media in delivering

teaching materials. This media is expected to support and facilitate students and teachers in teaching and learning, especially in teaching English more fun and exciting.

Han and Ling (2017) use Anime as a teaching media to teach Japanese as a foreign language. They found it is practical to use Anime in teaching Japanese. This study expects teachers to consider Anime as a teaching aid. The reason is that video is more acceptable by students due to the development of technology and students' familiarity with technology. Many studies have shown how cartoons can help raise students' better understanding of learning (Arikan & Taraf, 2010; Bahrani & Soltani, 2011; Munir, 2016, Velez Gea, 2013). However, those studies do not take place in Indonesia. Thus, this study tries to fill the gap by developing Anime to support one grammar lesson for teaching senior high school (i.e., tenses). By using 4D model by Thiagarajan et al., (1974), this study aimed at developing teaching media using *Anime* to increase students' grammar mastery and knowing the feasibility level of this learning media by trying it out in teaching tenses in one of the senior high schools in Sumatera.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Teaching Media. Teaching is an interactive process between the teacher and the students. According to Brown (2007), "Teaching is showing or helping someone to learn how to do something, giving instructions, guiding in the study of something, providing with knowledge, causing to know or understand" (p. 8). It is aimed to change one's behaviour by others. Media is a primary instrument in the teaching and learning process. It is used to attract the students' attention and deliver the information quickly. Media is a mode of communication as well as a source of information. The phrase is derived from the Latin word "between," and it refers to anything that transports data between a source and a recipient (Smaldino, Russel, Heinich & Molenda, 2004).

Teaching media is a tool to make the teaching and learning process more valuable. "a range of objects, pictures and other things can be used as instructional media to present and manipulate language and involve students in the activities" (Harmer, 2007, p. 177). Teaching media can invite students' attention and raise their curiosity by presenting various images and sounds. Teaching media can be used to present information that is needed to deliver the message to the students.

Teaching aids are used by teachers to stress material, pique students' attention, and make the learning process easier. They might be auditory, visual, or electronic, and they range from simple to sophisticated (Ruhis et al., 2009). By using teaching media, a teacher can make their class more exciting and efficient.

Teaching media are important educational resources that may help students learn more effectively and enjoyably. Media can play an essential role in teacher education because they allow us to save, alter, and share instructional content. Certain media allow us to record events as they occur, save them, and then use them afterwards. (Thiagarajan et al., 1974).

Moreover, there are several benefits to incorporating media into the teaching-learning process. These include increasing student motivation, avoiding boredom, making instructional content simple to grasp, and making the teaching-learning process more methodical. By offering diverse visuals and sounds, teaching media may draw students' attention and pique their interest. Teaching media may be used to convey information essential to get the point through to pupils (Sukartiwi in Ruhis et al., 2009).

English Grammar. We must understand grammar in order to learn English. Grammar is the collection of principles that allow us to assemble language words into big units (Greenbaum, 2002). The structure of words, phrases, clauses, and sentences are among the rules. Furthermore, according to Thornbury (1999), grammar describes the rules that control how sentences are created in a language.

English and Indonesian grammars have different features in sentence patterns. One of them is tenses, for example in English grammar syllable -ed on listened as the past form of listening as the present form. These different forms determine different meaning. The different features of these two kinds promote students' difficulty in understanding English grammar. In this study, the writer tried to develop a teaching media that contain English grammar materials for ten-grade at senior high school based on the syllabus and curriculum 2013. The tenses are simple present tense, present perfect tense, simple past tense, and past continuous tense.

Anime. What exactly is Anime? Anime is frequently associated with and likened to the notion of cartooning. Simply referring to Anime as "Japanese cartoons" does not convey the breadth and diversity of the genre. [...] Anime works essentially encompass everything that Western audiences are used to seeing in live-action films – romance, humour, tragedy, adventure, and even psychological probing of a type rarely seen in modern Western cinema or television. [...] Unlike cartoons in the West, Anime is a mainstream pop culture phenomenon in Japan (Napier, 2005).

The greatest approach to keep students interested and involved in lessons is to make them interactive (Barker, 2009). Teachers can enhance learners' observational, analytical, and higher-order thinking abilities by incorporating cartoons into the classroom with appropriate and practical activities. Teachers and students may use cartoons to start important conversations on topics including family life, social and current events, as well as moral ideals and religious views (Han & Ling, 2017).

Anime is derived from the term "animated" in English. Anime (pronounced 'ah-nee-may') is a Japanese animated film and television series, although the worlds of Anime go far beyond what is seen on screen. In its interwoven commercial and cultural activity webs that span industries and national lines, Anime is typical of contemporary media (Condry, 2003). Characters in Anime have large eyes, colourful hair, and a caricatured physique. All of these components convey connotations that are often exclusively understood by Japanese people.

III. METHODOLOGY

Method of Study. This study used a research development method oriented to produce products development of learning media in the education field. Research and development is an industry-based development approach in which research findings are utilised to build new products and methods that are then rigorously field-tested, assessed, and modified until they satisfy specified effectiveness, quality, or other requirements (Borg & Gall, 2003). The type of this research refers to the 4D model. Thiagarajan et al., (1974) divide the 4D model into four stages of defining, designing, developing, and disseminating. The implementation of this model was modified by researcher to correlate with this study. The product development description is explained by stating the steps to obtain the initial product, and then the writer takes a test to improve the product.

Research Participants. The subjects of this study are 35 students of tenth grade at one of the Senior High Schools in Sumatera. The validator subject of this study is media expert and material expert. Validity includes content and design. This validation aims to obtain the data in the form of judgment and advice. Then, the writer evaluated and revised the product. After that, the product was tried out to the students.

Technique for Collecting Data. In conducting this study, the writer collected the data with questionnaires as the instrument. According to Fraenkel (2011), "in a questionnaire, the subjects respond to the questions by writing or, more commonly, by marking an answer sheet" (p.125). Questionnaire was given to material expert, media expert and students. The expert questionnaire was used to know the appropriateness of the product from the expert. This questionnaire aims to evaluate the product before the students use it. Meanwhile, the student's questionnaire was to judge the product's design, content, and media component. The students chose their answers by check-marking the suitable box space based on four options. The topics of the questionnaire are curiosity, interest, attention, and happiness—the qualitative and quantitative data collected from this questionnaire.

Technique for Analyzing Data. The writer used descriptive statistic to analyze the data. The descriptive analysis uses only a few indices, such as the mean and median, to convey the information contained in a large number of scores (Frankael, 2011). The data obtained from this study was analysed through quantitative and qualitative analyses. The qualitative analysis was used to describe the result of the experts' suggestion. The data was analyzed by using descriptive statistic. The suggestion would be used to evaluate and revise the product. The questionnaires were analyzed by applying scales. There were ten items, and four options of the answers. The score were calculated and divided by the total of the items to get the mean of the score.

Figure 1 . Development Procedure

IV. DISCUSSION

Results

Description of Teaching Media Development. The results were obtained based on the development procedure on the 4D model (four-D) which has been defined in the previous part (define, design, development, and disseminate).

a. Define

The result of define on subjects of English was obtained in the form of curriculum and syllabus for the tenth grade at senior high school. It was used as media development guideline, besides that the writers determined media maker devices, media usage, *Anime* and material of English grammar to be developed. Teaching media that was made contained English grammar material for tenth grade. They are present perfect tense, simple past tense, would like to and be going to.

b. Design

After obtaining the material to make the learning media in the definition stage (define), then the writers designed teaching media and discussed the design. At this stage all the material that has been collected was turned into video animation. The design of media includes:

1. Storyboard.

2. The arrangement of material in the media includes the layout used.
3. Preparation of material that refers to the contextual model and visualized with the use of video animation

c. Develop

At this stage, the writers used some software to make the media such as SonyVegas pro 10, Microsoft power point 2010, VLC, adobePhotoshop, and GOM player. The design that has been done was developed through product validation. This validation process was done by media and materials experts.

d. Disseminate

After all the steps passed, this product was tried out. The writers hope this product can increase students' English grammar mastery. The product was integrated in youtube so the students can access it at school and home.

Data analyses. The data of product assessment is obtained in several stages. The first stage was obtained from the assessment of teaching media from one lecturer of English Education Department as a material expert, the second stage was obtained from the assessment of the teaching media conducted by one lecturer of Information Engineering Department at one of the private universities in Sumatera. The last stage obtained from 35 students' feedback.

Material Expert Validation. The products of development and questionnaire were assessed by the material expert. Validator test is tested by one of the lecturers from English Education department. The result of quantitative data from material expert can be seen in table 1.

No	Aspect Assessment	The highest number of answers(x _i)	Number of assessment answers(x)	Percentage of validity levels(P)
1.	content	21	24	$P = \frac{\sum x}{\sum xi} \times 100$
2.	ilustration	15	16	$P = \frac{36}{40} \times 100$ = 90%
	total	36	40	Very Feasible

Table 1. Material expert

The feasibility of the product based on the validation of material experts is 90%, including criteria for "feasible" to be used based on the feasibility qualification level table.

Percentage (%)	Feasibility criteria	information
84-100	Strongly feasible	No revise
68-84	feasible	No revise
52-68	Less feasible	Need revise
20-52	Not feasible	revise

Table 2. Feasibility qualification level

From the validation results, it is known that the teaching media has entered the criteria of "feasible" to be used, but still need improvement on the content of media based on the advice and suggestion that given by the material expert. The sample suggestions from the material experts can be seen in Table 3.

Validator	Data description	suggestion
Lecturer		Overall all the video is ready to use but the writers should Check the backsound noise

Table 3. Sample Suggestion from Material Expert

Media Expert Validation. The result of quantitative data from material expert can be seen in table 4.

No	Aspect Assessment	The highest number of answers(x _i)	Number of assessment answers(x)	Percentage of validity levels (P)
1.	display	17	20	$P = \frac{\sum x}{\sum xi} \times 100$
2.	Media usage	18	20	$P = \frac{35}{40} \times 100$ = 88%
	Total	35	40	Very Feasible

Table 4. Data Analysis of Media Expert's Assessment

The feasibility of the product based on the validation of media experts is 88%, including criteria "very feasible" to be used based on the feasibility qualification level table 5

Percentage (%)	Feasibility criteria	information
84-100	Strongly feasible	No revise
68-84	feasible	No revise
52-68	Less feasible	Need revise
20-52	Not feasible	revise

Tabel 5. Feasibility qualification level

From the validation results, it is known that the teaching media has entered the criteria of "very feasible" to be used, but still need improvement on the content of media based on the advice that given by the material expert. The suggestions from the material experts can be seen in Table 6.

No.	Content of video	Suggestion
1.		Not all infocus can show white so change the color
2.		Give narration in opening of video and check the grammar and spelling
3.		Give transition effect in every layout
4.		Give intro in closing

Table 6. List of Suggestions from Material Expert

Analyzing Students' Feedback. The result of students' feedback can be seen in table 7. After obtaining the data from the results of students' feedback that has been presented in table 7 above, the writers analyzed the data by using the formula below.

$$P = \frac{\sum x}{\sum x_i} \times 100\%$$

P = Percentage of validity levels
 $\sum x$ = The highest number of answers
 $\sum x_i$ = Number of assessment answers

the feasibility of the product based on the students' feedback is 86,78%, including criteria "**very feasible**" to be used based on the feasibility qualification level table.

Discussion

This teaching media is a research development to facilitate the teacher in delivering the material both in the classroom or outside the class. With this media, students are expected to learn optimally and has an impact on student learning outcomes. Beside that this teaching media is expected to have an impact in improving students' interest in learning English grammar that is considered boring by most of the students. Based on the findings of above, the interpretations are presented. They are:

First the result of the material expert validation. The material experts' validation results are reviewed from two main aspects, learning and material aspects. The result of the total score is including criteria "very feasible" to be used based on the feasibility qualification level table. but it still needs to revise the content of media based on the advice and suggestion given by the material expert. The suggestion is the writers should check again background of the video because it can disturb the concentration of the students.

Second the result of the media expert validation. The material experts' validation results are reviewed from two main aspects, display and media usage aspects. The result of the total score is including criteria "very feasible" to be used based on the feasibility qualification level table but it still need revise on the content of media based on the advice and suggestion that given by the material expert. The suggestion from the expert are (1) change the color of the sentences because not all in focus can show white color. (2) give narration in opening of video (3) give transition effect in every layout to make the viewer know the different layout (4) the opening of video is not really clear so the writers should add intro in closing.

Third the result of students feedback. The result of student feedback includes criteria "very feasible" to be used based on the feasibility qualification level table. It means teaching media can be use with no revise.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Most Indonesian students face difficulties in learning English grammar because the grammatical rules of Bahasa Indonesia are different from English's grammar. There is a need for new teaching materials which can help students in their learning. Video is an effective alternative teaching media for teaching English grammar. However, *Anime* contains real-life activities that can be combined into new material in teaching English grammar. For this study, the writers developed teaching media on English grammar for senior high school. The writers used pieces scene of Anime and software to develop the material. The new teaching media developed in this study for teaching have received very positive feedback and favorable comments from students and experts. This finding supports the finding from Han and Ling (2017) that Anime can support teaching language because it helps students increase their understanding in a relax situation as if they are watching. The conclusion is using Anime as teaching media especially in English creates a new learning situation that learning can be done through video (ie., cartoon and Anime) (Barker, 2009).

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